

Benchmarking semi-classical simulation schemes for molecular dynamics in the strong coupling regime

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Abstract

Experiments suggest that collectively coupling molecules to optical cavities can alter their photochemistry. To understand such cavity effects in atomic detail, semi-classical molecular dynamics have been introduced that can model the collective interaction of many molecules with chemical accuracy within the Tavis-Cummings framework of quantum optics. Here, we verify the validity of three such semi-classical approaches, namely Ehrenfest, Fewest-Switches Surface Hopping (FSSH) and the multi-state mapping approach to surface hopping (MS-MASH), for modeling the dynamics of strongly-coupled carbon-monoxide molecules against full quantum dynamics simulations with the multi-configuration time-dependent Hartree (MCTDH) method. The trajectories obtained with the semi-classical schemes agree qualitatively with the results of the quantum dynamics simulations, with FSSH providing the best quantitative agreement when a decoherence correction is applied. Our results thus suggest that semi-classical approaches can provide a valid alternative to quantum dynamics methods for modeling photochemistry in the collective strong coupling regime, for systems that are too large or complex for a fully quantum mechanical treatment.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, significant efforts have focused on engineering materials capable of precisely controlling the properties of light. The reverse process of controlling the fundamental properties of materials using light represents a far greater challenge but also a profound opportunity. Recent experiments suggest that optical resonators, such as cavities and plasmonic lattices, may provide such control. Indeed, embedding materials inside optical cavities has been demonstrated to reshape their physico-chemical properties, influencing energy transport [1–9], charge mobility [10–13], lasing thresholds [14, 15], and even photo-chemistry [16–20]. The possibility of harnessing cavity effects to steer photochemical reactions could open the door to transformative applications in artificial light harvesting, energy storage, and quantum technologies. Yet, despite its promise, progress in this new field of polaritonic chemistry is significantly hampered by a lack of theoretical understanding.

Optical resonators, such as a Fabry-Pérot microcavity, enhance light-matter interactions by confining the electromagnetic field into very small volumes [21]. If the strength of the light-matter interaction becomes sufficiently high, which can be achieved by increasing confinement or by increasing the *collective* oscillator strength of the material with more molecules, the system can enter the *strong coupling* regime, where quantum transitions in the material (*e.g.*, electronic or vibrational transitions) hybridize with the confined photon modes of the optical resonator [22, 23]. These light-matter hybrid states are called *polaritons* and are characterized by a Rabi splitting of the coupled material’s absorption spectrum into an upper and lower polariton. Because these polaritonic states are coherent superpositions of molecular transitions and cavity modes, an excitation is delocalized over many molecules. In addition to these bright and delocalized polaritonic states, also “dark” states form, which are the remaining superpositions that lack cavity mode contribution.

Because changes in material properties have so far only been observed in combination with Rabi splitting, these changes have been attributed to polaritons [23]. However, there is currently no consensus on why polariton formation would affect photochemistry, in particular, because the large majority of states are dark and hence similar to the uncoupled molecular states [24, 25].

The paradox of polaritonic chemistry is that under the collective strong coupling conditions in optical cavities, an excitation is coherently shared by many molecules, whereas

chemistry involves only a few. Although the underlying physics of light-matter interactions in the strong coupling regime is known [?], the challenge facing theoretical efforts at resolving this paradox is to model such interactions for a sufficiently large number of molecules with chemical accuracy. To circumvent modeling large numbers of molecules, most theoretical approaches focus on single molecules instead, using much stronger cavity vacuum fields [26–36]. Because the Rabi splitting scales with the number of molecules, N , as \sqrt{N} [22], these fields are enhanced by the same factor to achieve strong coupling with only a single molecule. However, such scaled fields can easily become nonphysical [37], and hence induce changes to the photo-chemistry that are not real. On the other hand, models from quantum optics that focus on describing collective strong coupling in large N limit [38–40], tend to lack chemical details that are needed to unravel how the coherent coupling impacts the chemistry locally.

To overcome the limitations of these two modeling extremes for modeling electronic strong coupling, a divide-and-conquer strategy was proposed. Combining the Born-Oppenheimer and long-wavelength approximations, polaritonic states are obtained within the Tavis-Cummings (TC) framework of quantum optics using the adiabatic electronic ground and excited states of the molecules evaluated at a suitable level of quantum chemistry, as the basis [41, 42]. By propagating the nuclear degrees of freedom classically under the influence of the polaritonic wavefunction, while simultaneously propagating that wavefunction as a time-dependent superposition of the TC eigenstates along the classical trajectory, the molecular dynamics (MD) in the collective strong coupling regime can be modeled with chemical accuracy [43, 44]. Through extensive parallelization, such semi-classical MD simulations of thousands of molecules in Fabry-Pérot micro-cavities helped resolve important questions, such as: (*i*) why, despite the short lifetimes of cavity modes, the polariton appears long-lived [43, 45]; (*ii*) why polariton transport is not ballistic but diffusive [46, 47] and can even reverse on longer timescales [48]; and (*iii*) what is the role of molecular disorder on polaritonic effects [25, 45].

However, with Newton’s equations of motion governing the propagation of the nuclear degrees of freedom, semi-classical ansätze neglect nuclear quantum effects. To understand the impact of this approximation on the computed dynamics under electronic strong coupling, we here compare semi-classical trajectories of polaritonic systems to the results of fully quantum dynamics simulations. To keep the latter simulations tractable, we focus on up to

four carbon-monoxide (CO) molecules strongly coupled to a single-mode optical cavity that is resonant with the optical transition into the electronically excited ${}^1\Pi$ state. The paper is organized as follows: In section II, we present our model of a CO in a single-mode optical cavity and share the details of our simulations on this system. Then, in section III we compare the observables obtained from semi-classical and quantum dynamics simulations for a varying number of CO molecules coupled to the cavity. Finally, we conclude in section IV with a summary and outlook.

II. COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

A. Potential energy surfaces

The equilibrium geometry of the electronic ground state (S_0) of CO was optimized with the Gaussian09 program [49] at the coupled-cluster singles and doubles (CCSD) level of *ab initio* theory employing the augmented correlation-consistent polarized valence double zeta (aug-cc-pVDZ) basis set. The S_0 minimum energy geometry has a $C_{\infty v}$ point group symmetry with an equilibrium bond length of 1.1405 Å and a fundamental anharmonic frequency of 2172 cm^{-1} .

The potential energy curves and dipole moments as a function of the CO bond length were calculated with the MOLPRO program package [50] at the CASSCF(14,10)/aug-cc-pVDZ level of multi-configuration self-consistent field theory, with state-averaging over the six lowest-energy singlet electronic states. Energies, dipole moments, and transition dipole moments (TDM) were calculated for eighty inter nuclear distances between 0.7 Å (~ 1.3 a.u.) and 2.3 Å (~ 4.3 a.u.). The energy profiles for electric ground state (${}^1\Sigma$) and for one of the doubly degenerate electronic excited states (${}^1\Pi$) are shown in Fig. 1a, along with the transition dipole moment between these states [cf. Fig. 1b].

A Morse potential was fitted to each potential energy profile [cf. Fig. 1(a)]:

$$V_i(R) = E_i + D_i [1 - \exp(-\alpha_i(R - R_i^{\text{eq}}))]^2 \quad (1)$$

with R_i^{eq} is the equilibrium C-O distance, and D_i the dissociation energy in the ground ($i = 0$) and excited state ($i = 1$), respectively. The values of these fitting parameters are

FIG. 1. Adiabatic potential energy curves of the bare CO molecule (a), and transition dipole moment curve between the ground $^1\Sigma$ and the first excited $^1\Pi$ electronic states (b). PESs of one CO molecule in a cavity: The coupling strength is equal to zero (c) and 0.050 (d). The PES without coupling shows the energy of the ground state shifted to the energy mode of the cavity (i.e. cavity mode excitation, $V_0 + \omega_c$), as well as the ground and excited states of the CO molecule. Panel (b) shows the hybrid states as result of the coupling between the cavity and the molecule. These cuts are obtained by the diagonalization of the cavity and electronic Hamiltonian [cf. Eq. 9].

provided in Table I.

TABLE I. Morse potential fitting parameters (in a.u.) for both $^1\Sigma^+$ and $^1\Pi$ electronic states

Parameters	$^1\Sigma$	$^1\Pi$
E_i	0.0000	0.3311
D_i	0.4013	0.1086
α_i	1.2710	1.4144
R_i^{eq}	2.15	2.42

B. Quantum dynamics simulations of strongly coupled CO molecules

1. Molecule-cavity Hamiltonian

We consider a one-dimensional array of N identical and non-interacting CO molecules inside an optical cavity. The molecular ensemble-cavity Hamiltonian contains a molecular part, cavity part and their interaction:

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{k=1}^N \hat{H}_{\text{mol}}^{(k)} + \hat{H}_{\text{cav}} + \hat{H}_{\text{cav-mol}} \quad (2)$$

with $\hat{H}_{\text{mol}}^{(k)} = \hat{T}_n^{(k)} + \hat{H}_e^{(k)}$ the Hamiltonian of the k^{th} CO molecule, including the kinetic and potential energy operators of the bare molecule:

$$\hat{H}_{\text{mol}} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial R^2} \mathbf{1} + \begin{pmatrix} V_0(R) & 0 \\ 0 & V_1(R) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where μ is the reduced nuclear mass, R is the C-O internuclear distance, and $V_0(R)$ and $V_1(R)$ the potential energy curves in the electronic ground and excited states, respectively (Fig. 1a), fitted to Morse potentials (Equation 1).

Within the long-wavelength approximation, the Hamiltonian describing the cavity mode and its interaction with the molecules is [26, 27, 41, 51–54]

$$\hat{H}_{\text{cav}} + \hat{H}_{\text{cav-mol}} = \hbar\omega_c \left(\frac{1}{2} + \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} \right) + g \vec{D} \cdot \vec{\epsilon}_c (\hat{a}^\dagger + \hat{a}) \quad (4)$$

Here, ω_c the cavity mode frequency, \hat{a}^\dagger and \hat{a} the photon creation and annihilation operators, respectively, g the coupling strength defined as $g = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega_c}{2V\epsilon_0}}$, \vec{D} the molecular dipole operator, and $\vec{\epsilon}_c$ the cavity mode polarization. For simplicity, we only consider a single polarization direction.

2. Quantum dynamics propagation

The time evolution of the molecular ensemble-cavity wave function is computed using the multi-configuration time dependent hartree (MCTDH) approach [55, 56] implemented in the

Heidelberg MCTDH program version 86.2 [57]. In this approach, the wave function is approximated as a product of time-dependent coefficients with time-dependent basis functions for each nuclear, electronic, and cavity degree of freedom. Within this formalism, the cavity mode is treated as an harmonic oscillator in terms of the position ($\hat{q}_c = \sqrt{\hbar/2\omega_c}[\hat{a}^\dagger + \hat{a}]$) and momentum operators ($\hat{p}_c = i\sqrt{\hbar\omega_c/2}[\hat{a}^\dagger - \hat{a}]$) rather than the annihilation and creation operators in Equation 4 [53, 54, 58, 59].

To facilitate comparison with semi-classical molecular dynamics simulations, in which the photo-excitation is modeled as an instantaneous population transfer into one of the polaritonic states, we generate the initial state for the MCTDH simulations through application of the operator \hat{T}_\pm , which directly excites the cavity-molecule system to a 1:1 light-matter superposition state (with the minus sign in the index for LP and plus for UP) [58]

$$\hat{T}_\pm = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\hat{a}^\dagger + \hat{a}) \mp \sum_{\kappa}^N \frac{1}{\sqrt{2N}} (|0_\kappa\rangle\langle 1_\kappa| + \text{h.c.}). \quad (5)$$

3. Wavefunction analysis

The populations of the UP and LP states are the key observables characterizing the time-evolution of the hybrid system. A convenient way to extract such information from the MCTDH wavefunction is to compute the expectation value of the light-matter interaction term in the Hamiltonian divided by the interaction strength:[58, 59]

$$V_{\text{int,r}} = \langle \Psi(t) | \hat{O} | \Psi(t) \rangle \quad (6)$$

with

$$\hat{O} = -(\hat{a}^\dagger + \hat{a}) \sum_{\kappa} (|0_\kappa\rangle\langle 1_\kappa| + |1_\kappa\rangle\langle 0_\kappa|) \quad (7)$$

where $|0_\kappa\rangle$ and $|1_\kappa\rangle$ are the two electronic states of the κ^{th} CO molecule coupled by the optical cavity mode. Because the LP and UP states correspond to positive and negative linear combinations of the electronic and photonic excitations, $V_{\text{int,r}}$ approaches -1 for the LP and 1 for the UP.

C. Semi-classical molecular dynamics simulations of strongly coupled CO molecules

Starting from the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, we separate the electronic plus cavity mode degrees of freedom from the nuclear degrees of freedom [41]. Neglecting the dipole-self energy, which is very small for realistic cavity setups [37], and adopting the rotating wave approximation (RWA), valid when the cavity mode and molecular excitation are resonant, we can recast the light-matter interaction in Equation 4 into the Tavis-Cummings Hamiltonian [60, 61]:

$$\hat{H}^{\text{TC}} = \omega_c \left(\frac{1}{2} + \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} \right) + g \vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{\epsilon}_c (\hat{a}^\dagger + \hat{a}) \quad (8)$$

Within the single excitation manifold, valid for the weak driving typically employed in experiments, this Hamiltonian can be represented in the basis of product states formed from the adiabatic electronic excitations of the molecules and the cavity mode [42]:

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{i=1}^N V_0(R_i) \mathbf{1}_N + \begin{pmatrix} \hbar\omega_c & \gamma(R_1) & \gamma(R_2) & \cdots \\ \gamma(R_1) & \Delta(R_1) & 0 & \cdots \\ \gamma(R_2) & 0 & \Delta(R_2) & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is a unit matrix of dimension N , $V_0(R_i)$ is the ground state potential energy of the i th molecule, $\Delta(R_i) = V_1(R_i) - V_0(R_i)$ is the vertical change in potential energy upon excitation, and the dipole coupling of the i th molecule to the cavity mode is $\gamma(R_i) = g_0 d_{01}(R_i)$, d_{01} being the dipole transition moment of the molecule along the cavity polarization axis.

Diagonalizing the matrix representation in the basis of the single-excitation product states (Equation 9) of the multi-scale Tavis-Cummings Hamiltonian (Equation 2) yields the $N + n_{\text{mode}}$ adiabatic hybrid light-matter eigenstates, $|\psi^m\rangle$:

$$|\psi^m\rangle = \left(\sum_j^N \beta_j^m \hat{\sigma}_j^+ + \sum_p^{n_{\text{mode}}} \alpha_p^m \hat{a}_p^\dagger \right) |\phi_0\rangle \quad (10)$$

with eigenenergies E_m . The β_j^m and α_p^m expansion coefficients reflect the contribution of the molecular excitations, $|S_1^j(\mathbf{R}_j)\rangle$, and the cavity mode excitations, $|1_p\rangle$, to polariton $|\psi^m\rangle$. Due to their parametric dependence on the nuclear degrees of freedom, these eigenenergies

form adiabatic potential energy surfaces $E_m(\mathbf{R})$, with \mathbf{R} the $3 \times N_{\text{mol}} \times N_{\text{atoms}}$ coordinates of all atoms in the system [41, 62]. Polaritonic surfaces for a single CO molecule coupled to the cavity are shown in Fig. 1d.

In semi-classical dynamics simulations, nuclear trajectories are evolved by numerically integrating Newton’s equations of motion under the influence of the forces due to the quantum degrees of freedom, for which the wave function, $|\Psi(t)\rangle$, is propagated along the classical trajectory. To model the non-adiabatic dynamics in the manifold of eigenstates (Equation 10), we used three popular approaches: (i) Ehrenfest; (ii) fewest-switches surface hopping [63, 64] with and (iii) without decoherence correction [65] and (iv) the Mapping approach to Surface Hopping (MASH) [66, 67]. The details of their implementation for semi-classical molecular dynamics in the collective strong coupling regime are described in Sokolovskii and Groenhof [44].

All semi-classical simulations were performed with GROMACS version 4.5.4, using a timestep of 0.1 fs. For each semi-classical method and single-molecule coupling strength, g , 200 non-adiabatic trajectories were computed with an integration time step of 0.1 fs. The starting coordinates and velocities were randomly sampled from a Wigner distribution at 0 K and observables were averaged over the trajectories.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Bare CO dynamics

Before focusing on the dynamics of CO molecules in a cavity, we first simulate and compare the dynamics of a single CO molecule in vacuum. In Figure 2a we show the linear absorption spectrum of a bare CO molecule obtained with MCTDH and classical molecular dynamics simulations. In the MCTDH simulations, the ground-state vibrational wavefunction, $|\psi(0)\rangle$ was promoted from the electronic ground to excited state and propagated for 200 fs. The overlap, $S(t) = \langle \psi(0) | \psi(t) \rangle$ was computed, multiplied with an empirical damping function $e^{-t/\tau}$ ($\tau = 3$ fs) and Fourier transformed into the linear absorption spectrum shown in Figure 2a. The classical absorption spectrum was obtained a sum of the vertical excitation energies along MD trajectories, convolved with either a gaussian (width, $\sigma=0.2$ eV) or a Lorentzian (half-width at half maximum, $\gamma=0.2$ eV) functions. Whereas both con-

volution schemes provide satisfactory agreement with the MCTDH spectrum, the absorption lineshape matches the MCTDH result more closely with the Gaussian convolution.

FIG. 2. (a) The linear absorption spectrum of bare CO molecule of the $^1\Pi$ electronic state is evaluated using both MCTDH (solid line) and MD with Gaussian (dashed dot), and Lorentzian (dashed line) functions. (b) Expectation value of the inter-nuclear distance, $\langle R \rangle$, as a function of time after instantaneous excitation into the first excited electronic state of the CO molecule.

In Figure 2b, we plot the CO bond length as a function of time after instantaneous excitation from the $^1\Sigma$ electronic ground state into the $^1\Pi$ excited state for both MCTDH and classical MD simulations. The classical result was averaged over 100 trajectories, initiated with different initial positions and velocities, sampled from the Wigner distribution at 0 K in the $^1\Sigma$ electronic ground state. Despite small deviations, in particular at longer timescales, the dynamics are qualitatively similar, providing an good starting point for exploring nuclear quantum effects in the electronic strong coupling regime of this system.

B. Single molecule strong coupling

When placing a single CO molecule at the anti-node of a cavity mode with a sufficiently strong vacuum field, the molecular and cavity mode excitations hybridize into an upper and lower polariton state, separated by Rabi splitting. Because the Rabi splitting depends critically on the detuning and transition dipole moment, the potential energy surfaces of these hybrid states are different from the uncoupled states [41]. As shown in Fig. 1c, for a cavity mode on resonance with the vertical excitation energy at the V_0 minimum of the

bare CO molecule, the surface associated with the LP is lower in energy than the uncoupled $^1\Pi$ excited state (V_1), and has a deeper local minimum, whereas the UP is higher in energy than the uncoupled $^1\Sigma$ ground state ($V_0 + \omega_c$).

To verify whether semi-classical MD simulations can capture the effects of these modifications on the nuclear dynamics, we compare expectation values from semi-classical trajectories to those from an MCTDH calculations. Fig. 3 shows the time evolution of the electronic populations when the molecular system is selectively excited into one of the hybrid states (LP or UP) at different coupling strengths. The left panels (a-e) correspond to Ehrenfest dynamics, while the right panels (f-j) represent the MCTDH results. Overall, the two approaches are in good agreement, demonstrating consistent population dynamics. However, there are noticeable deviations when the system is excited into the UP state (i.e. UP populations) at the longer time scales and under weak coupling conditions [cf. panels a-e of Fig. 3]. This is because Ehrenfest dynamics cannot capture quantum coherence properly under weak coupling.

FIG. 3. Time-dependence of electronic population, when the molecule is excitation to the LP (solid lines)/UP (dashed lines) state at different coupling strengths. The electronic populations from the MD simulations are averaged over 100 initial conditions sampled from a Wigner distribution.

Fig. 4 illustrates the time-evolution of the cavity-molecule interaction potential $V_{\text{int},r}$ [cf. Eq. 6] for a single CO molecule strongly coupled to a cavity mode, after excitation into the LP (solid line) and UP (dashed lines) states at different coupling strengths obtained from full-quantum (MCTDH) simulations (upper row), Ehrenfest MD (middle row) and FSSH MD (bottom row). For all coupling strengths considered, $V_{\text{int},r}$ exhibits oscillatory behavior, reflecting smooth adiabatic passage between regions on the polaritonic potential energy surfaces with different molecular and photonic contributions (Equation 10). The decrease of the oscillation period of $V_{\text{int},r}$ in the LP with increasing coupling strength, is in line with a deepening of the local minimum on the LP surface [62]. This effect is captured in both Ehrenfest and FSSH MD. The data furthermore suggest that there is no non-adiatic population transfer between the UP and LP. Overall, these results demonstrate that both Ehrenfest and SH methods qualitatively capture the essential features of the polaritonic dynamics.

C. Multiple molecules

When more than one molecule interacts with a single cavity mode, the collective light-matter coupling modifies the polaritonic states in a nontrivial manner. To ensure that the overall Rabi splitting remains constant when we increase the number of molecules N , we scale down the single-molecule cavity-molecule coupling constant, g , as $g \rightarrow g/\sqrt{N}$. This scaling maintains the collective coupling strength while allowing us to systematically investigate cooperative effects arising from multiple molecules inside the cavity.

First, we consider two CO molecules strongly coupled to a single-photon cavity mode. Diagonalization of the Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} [cf. Eq. 9] yields three distinct eigenstates [cf. Fig. S4 of the SI]: two bright polaritonic states (LP and UP) and one dark state, which is degenerate with the molecular excited state. Fig. 5 illustrates the time-dependent dynamics of the cavity-molecule interaction potential, $V_{\text{int},r}$, for the two-molecule system at different coupling strengths ($g = 0.030, 0.040, 0.050$), in MCTDH, Ehrenfest, FSSH with and without decoherence, and MS-MASH simulations.

FIG. 4. The cavity-molecule interaction potential V_{intr} , when the single CO molecule is interacting with the cavity mode and excitation into the LP (solid lines)/UP (dashed lines) states at different coupling strengths. The MD simulations are averaged over 100 initial conditions of Morse potential sampled from a Wigner distribution. In the case of Ehrenfest dynamics, we tried with both HO and Morse model for the Wigner sampling. A value of $V_{intr} = -1$, and 1 denotes that the population remains trapped in the LP and UP state, respectively.

1. MCTDH dynamics (top row):

The MCTDH results, representing the full quantum dynamics, serve as the benchmark for evaluating all other approaches. In each panel, the solid and dashed lines correspond to the initial excitation into the LP and UP, respectively. Across all coupling strengths, the dynamics of the populations in the LP and UP states evolves differently. Whereas the dynamics in the LP state is mostly adiabatic, as evidenced by the oscillations in $V_{int,r}$ that imply periodic sampling of different regions on the lowest potential energy surface, the decay

of $V_{\text{int},r}$ in the UP states suggest efficient population transfer into the dark states, where it remains trapped.

As the coupling strength increases from $g= 0.030$ to 0.050 , the oscillation frequency of $V_{\text{int},r}$ increases due to enhanced Rabi splitting, suggesting a trapping of the population in deepening local minimum on the LP surface. This thus leads to the suppression of photodynamics proposed by Galego *et al.*[62]. The rate at which population is transferred from the UP state into the dark states decreases upon increasing the coupling strength. We attribute this suppression of non-adiabatic population transfer to the increased energy gap between the UP and the dark states, which reduces the non-adiabatic coupling.

2. Ehrenfest dynamics (second row):

The Ehrenfest MD simulations qualitatively reproduces the oscillatory features observed in MCTDH but display a much faster damping and a reduction in oscillation amplitude, in particular for the dynamics initiated in the LP. We attribute this discrepancy to an overestimation of coherence losses in the mean-field approximation. The population transfer from the UP in the dark states is slower compared to the MCTDH simulations, in particular for larger coupling strengths.

3. Fewest Switches Surface Hopping (third row):

The FSSH simulations also reproduce the key dynamical features of the LP and UP states but are strongly influenced by whether decoherence corrections are included or not. Without decoherence (orange and blue lines labeled SH), the populations behave similarly to those from Ehrenfest dynamics, maintaining excess coherence and slower relaxation. When decoherence corrections (purple and green lines, SH+decoh) are included, the LP dynamics display a marked improvement, aligning more closely with the full quantum MCTDH results. However, both with and without decoherence corrections, the FSSH approach underestimates population transfer from the UP state into the dark state. This discrepancy indicates that additional decoherence mechanisms or stochastic averaging may be needed for more accurate long-time behavior.

FIG. 5. The cavity-molecule interaction potential V_{intr} , when the two CO molecules are interacting with cavity mode and excitation into the LP (solid lines)/UP (dashed lines) states at different coupling strengths. The MD simulations are averaged over 100 initial conditions sampled from a Wigner distribution.

4. MS-MASH dynamics (bottom row):

Employing the MASH scheme in our semi-classical dynamics, we obtain dynamics that are similar to the Ehrenfest dynamics but with slightly enhanced oscillation amplitudes for the LP excitation. As the other semi-classical methods, MS-MASH underestimates the population transfer from the UP into the dark state.

These results demonstrate that FSSH can reproduce the main dynamical signatures of light-matter hybridization quantum effects for two CO molecules in a cavity, but at different timescales. We thus conclude that when the coupling is not too large, semiclassical molecular dynamics can provide computationally efficient yet physically reasonable alternative for modeling the cavity-molecule interactions if quantum dynamics is computationally too expensive.

FIG. 6. Same as Fig. 5, when the four CO molecules are interacting with the cavity mode.

Finally, we increase the number of CO molecules in the cavity to four. In Fig. 6 we plot the interaction potential, $V_{\text{int},r}$ for a vertical excitation into the LP or UP states. The overall dynamical behavior follows similar trends to the two-molecules case, as discussed above. However, the collective coupling leads to enhanced stability of the LP state and a faster decay of the UP population, consistent with the emergence of additional dark states in the multi-molecule configuration. These results underline the cooperative nature of molecular-cavity coupling and its impact on the redistribution of excitation energy among polaritonic and dark manifolds.

While Ehrenfest and MASH FSSH without decoherence corrections now capture the decay from the UP into the dark states, including decoherence corrections to FSSH suppresses this dephasing process. We attribute this to an over-correction of the decoherence, in particular when the non-adiabatic coupling is small. More problematic is the rapid relaxation of population from the LP into the dark states, which is happening at a much faster rate for the semi-classical approaches compared to MCTDH, even for the largest coupling strengths.

This is a major discrepancy, and can lead to qualitatively incorrect results.

IV. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

In this work, we systematically investigated the nonadiabatic dynamics of CO molecules strongly coupled to an optical cavity, combining full quantum and semi-classical molecular dynamics approaches. The light–matter interaction was modeled through a molecule–cavity Hamiltonian, and the MCTDH method was employed to obtain reference quantum dynamics results. The time-dependent populations of the upper and lower polaritonic states, as well as the cavity–molecule interaction potentials, were analyzed to characterize the coherent energy exchange between photonic and molecular degrees of freedom.

To assess the performance of computationally efficient semi-classical methods, three widely used approaches Ehrenfest dynamics, FSSH, and MS-MASH were benchmarked against the MCTDH results. The comparison revealed that, while the Ehrenfest approach captures the overall oscillatory features of polaritonic energy exchange, it tends to overestimate coherence loss due to its mean-field nature. The FSSH method, particularly when augmented with decoherence corrections, provided the closest quantitative agreement with the fully quantum simulations, accurately reproducing both the Rabi oscillation period and the population transfer between polaritonic states. The MS-MASH approach also performed well, maintaining a balance between computational efficiency and physical accuracy, though with slightly reduced fidelity in describing population transfer from the UP state.

The results demonstrate that semi-classical molecular dynamics methods can reliably reproduce the key dynamical signatures of strong light–matter coupling, including Rabi oscillations, and population exchange, when appropriately parameterized. Importantly, the inclusion of decoherence effects is crucial for achieving quantitative consistency with quantum benchmarks. These findings suggest that semi-classical approaches, especially FSSH with decoherence, can serve as viable alternatives to fully quantum treatments like MCTDH, particularly for larger or more complex systems where full quantum propagation becomes computationally intractable.

Looking forward, the methodological insights gained here provide a foundation for exploring collective polaritonic effects in multi-molecule systems, as demonstrated by our simulations of two and four CO molecules interacting with a single cavity mode. The observed

scaling of Rabi splitting with the number of molecules confirms the cooperative nature of the coupling and highlights the potential of these approaches for studying collective strong-coupling phenomena. Future extensions of this work will focus on including dissipative environments, and multi-mode cavities, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of polaritonic chemistry and light-induced reactivity in realistic condensed-phase environments.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY

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Supporting Material:
**Benchmarking semi-classical simulation schemes for molecular dynamics in the
strong coupling regime**

FIG. S1. Linear absorption spectrum for a resonant excitation into the $^1\Pi$ electronic state, when the molecule is without the cavity and a single molecule inside an optical cavity at different coupling strengths.

TABLE S1. Rabi splitting energy $\hbar\Omega_R$ (at the FC geometry), Rabi oscillation period τ_R , and polaritonic states energies (E_{LP} , E_{UP}), when the two CO molecules are coupled with a single cavity mode.

g (a.u.)	Ω_R (eV)	τ_R (fs)	E_{LP} (eV)	E_{UP} (eV)
0.001	0.0327	126.47	9.6095	9.6422
0.002	0.0653	63.33	9.5932	9.6585
0.003	0.0980	42.20	9.5768	9.6748
0.004	0.1307	31.64	9.5604	9.6911
0.005	0.1634	25.31	9.5440	9.7074
0.006	0.1960	21.10	9.5276	9.7237
0.008	0.2614	15.82	9.4948	9.7562
0.010	0.3267	12.66	9.4619	9.7886
0.020	0.6536	6.33	9.2967	9.9503
0.030	0.9809	4.22	9.1302	10.1110
0.040	1.3086	3.16	8.9623	10.2709
0.050	1.6369	2.53	8.7930	10.4299

FIG. S2. Expectation value of the cavity photon number $\langle N_{ph} \rangle = \langle \Psi(t) | \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} | \Psi(t) \rangle$ as a function of time.

FIG. S3. Linear absorption spectrum for an excitation into the molecular $^1\Pi$ electronic excited state (i.e., bare CO molecule, orange color) and the LP/UP state, when a single molecule inside an optical cavity at different coupling strengths, g .

FIG. S4. PESs of two CO molecules in a single cavity mode. The coupling strength considered here is 0.050. The PESs without coupling shows the energy of the ground state shifted to the energy mode of the cavity (i.e. cavity mode excitation, $V_0 + \omega_c$), as well as the ground and excited states of the CO molecule. The hybrid states as result of the coupling between the cavity and the molecule. These cuts are obtained by the diagonalization of the cavity and electronic Hamiltonian [cf. Eq. 9].